

Table 1. Root pulling force of hybrids, their parents, and check varieties. 1983 summer.

Hybrid, variety	Root pulling force (kg)
<i>F₁ hybrids</i>	
V20A/IR50	24.05*
V20A/IR54	25.15*
Z97A/IR50	23.98*
Z97A/IR54	25.10*
Z97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	22.90*
Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1	24.95*
Mean	24.36
<i>Parents</i>	
IR50	18.15
IR54	22.95
IR2307-247-2-2-3	17.90
IR13420-6-3-3-1	19.43
V20B	14.95
Z97B	17.15
Mean	18.43
<i>Checks</i>	
CR44-35	17.18
Sita	21.43
Mean	19.31
CD at 5%	1.23

varieties (Table 1). The highest root pulling force of 25.15 kg was for V20A/IR54, followed by 25.10 kg for Z97A/IR54 and 24.95 kg Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1.

All *F₁* hybrids showed positive heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for root pulling force

(Table 2). Highest heterosis and heterobeltiosis values were observed in V20A/IR50 and maximum standard heterosis value in Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1. A strong, deep, and active root system in hybrid rice may also have potential for its adaptation in rainfed uplands and lowlands. *S*

Table 2. Expression of heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis for root pulling force. 1983 summer.

Hybrid	Heterosis (%)	Heterobeltiosis (%)	Standard heterosis (%)
V20A/IR50	44.9	32.5	40.0
V20A/IR54	33.1	9.6	17.4
Z97A/IR50	35.5	32.1	39.6
Z97A/IR54	24.9	9.4	17.1
Z97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	30.9	27.9	33.3
Z97A/IR13420-6-7-3-1	36.4	28.4	45.2

Isolation of fertility restorers and maintainers for cytoplasmic genetic male sterile line

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Development of hybrid rice is possible only if the effective fertility restorers for cytoplasmic genetic male sterile (CMS) lines are identified or developed.

Isolation of maintainers for CMS lines is necessary for the development of new CMS lines.

We used the Chinese CMS line V20A as common female parent in crosses

List of complete restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers identified for CMS line V20A at Agricultural Research Institute, Patna, India, 1984.

Complete restorers	Partial restorers	Maintainers
CR289-1208	CR407-6-2	ADT30
CR75-93-Mut. 11-4	CR401-7	Bala
IR9703-4-1-3-3-1	CR167-7	CR407-19
IR2307-247-2-2-3	CR157-22-1900	CR200-788-3
Madhu	IR60	Dhaneshwar
	Pusa 205-15-1	Jikoku Sernai
	RP1451-2266-55-22	MR365
	RP732-26-2	Pusa 2-21
		Ramchure

with standard varieties and elite breeding lines. Percent spikelet fertility of *F₁* hybrids was used as fertility index. Lines that restored 80% or more spikelet fertility were classified as

complete restorers, those restoring between 20% and 79% fertility were partial restorers, and those with less than 20% were classified as maintainers (see table). *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

OTHER PESTS

Reaction of rice varieties to root nematode *Hirschmanniella* spp. in the field

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Seventeen rice varieties were evaluated for resistance to root nematode. The average initial population of *Hirschmanniella* spp. extracted from soil samples of the experimental field before planting was 145 nematodes/300 cc soil.

Each test variety was seeded and transplanted into 3 rows at 25- × 25-cm spacing, 10 hills/row.

At 60 d after transplanting, the final population of nematodes was extracted from soil taken from around the root zone in the middle row of each variety.